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Questioning techniques of teachers and speaking ability of students

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Abstract

The research study was brought about the urgency to determine the significant relationship of the questioning techniques of the teacher and speaking ability of students. The study employed a quantitative non-experimental research design utilizing a correlation technique which covered 316 respondents. Results show that the questioning techniques of teachers is high and the level of speaking ability of students is also high. However, there is no significant relationship between questioning techniques of teachers and the speaking ability of students. This means that the speaking ability of students is not influenced by the questioning techniques of teachers.

Keywords: questioning techniques, speaking ability, classroom management

Questioning techniques of teachers and speaking ability of students

1. Introduction

The classroom is a place of interaction between teachers and students. It is a setting that breeds numerous academic discourses for the participants. It is a place where learning occurs. An integral part of the learning process is the ability of the teacher to ask questions. The kind of questions that stir the mind of learn towards meaningful learning outcomes. When teachers ask questions, students are engaged with the content at the same time teachers can get feedback from their students (Long, 1980).

Previous studies were able to document the benefit that students get from the teachers using questioning techniques. Shanmugavelu et al. (2020) concluded that questioning techniques, enable teachers to explain content for students to understand. The same study even added that questions can even be used to promote critical thinking on students. In another study by Walsh and Sattes (2015), questioning techniques is used in the classroom discussion most particularly the quality of questions support engaging discussions. International studies have also noted that engagement within the classroom are effective techniques in enhancing student outcomes (Hu et al., 2012, 2015; De Guzman & Macapagal, 2020; Hsieh, 2016)

Speaking ability also has been explored in studies with diverse results. It was indicated by Leong and Ahmadi (2017), that speaking ability is influenced by motivation and anxiety. Thus, it is recommended in the study that students should have a positive environment that enables students to overcome challenges in oral performance. Tacadena (2021) adds that teachers that are centered on caring results in improved student learning. However, it was concluded by Pascual (2019) that there is no significant relationship between English linguistic environment and oral proficiency among students. The present study examined the questioning techniques of teachers and the speaking ability of the students. Questioning techniques and speaking ability is not new a concept in educational research however studies establishing the relationship between questioning techniques and speaking ability are sparse in the locale. This inspired the research to pursue the study. From this study, insights can be drawn from an experience that occurs in the classroom setting.

2. Methodology

This study employed a quantitative non-experimental research design. The design was specifically chosen by the researchers since the study is a noncausal statistical relationship between variables. This complies to Jhangiani et al. (2019). Specifically, the study is a correlational research which involved the relationship of two variables. The study sought to investigate the correlation between questioning techniques and speaking ability. The study involved 316 students of the Department of Arts and Sciences and Department of Teacher Education. As stated by Fraenkel and Wallen (2009), the sample size for correlational studies should be more than 30. A sample of size of 30 and beyond will give results that are meaningful. The statistical following statistical tools were used for data analysis and interpretation of the results.

Mean. This statistical tool will be used to determine the level of questioning techniques of teachers speaking ability of students.

Person(r). This statistical tool will be employed to determine the significance of the relationship between teachers' questioning techniques and students speaking ability

3. Results and findings

Level of Questioning techniques - As shown in table 1, the means scores for indicators of questioning techniques overall mean of 3.90 are described as high with a standard deviation of 0.40. It means that teachers

questioning techniques in terms of Rephrasing, Simplification, Repetition, Decomposition, and Probing are very much manifested by the teachers in class.

Table 1

Level of Teachers' Questioning Techniques

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
Rephrasing	3.92	0.49	High
Simplification	3.95	0.50	High
Repetition	3.89	0.49	High
Decomposition	3.90	0.51	High
Probing	3.85	0.46	High
Overall	3.90	0.40	High

The highest mean score is 3.95 for Simplification with a standard deviation of 0.50; This is followed by 3.92 for rephrasing questions with a standard deviation of 0.49; Decomposition got 3.90 with a standard deviation of 0.51; Repetition garnered 3.89 with a standard deviation of 0.49; finally, Probing got the lowest mean of 3.85 with a standard deviation of 0.46.

It can be observed that all indicators of Questioning techniques are all high which means that the teacher's questioning techniques are highly observed in all indicators. Teachers employ rephrasing wherein questions are expressed in another way for better understanding. Teachers also employ simplification. This means that teachers simplify questions for students to cope. Repetition is also employed where questions are repeated. Finally, teachers also employ decomposition wherein probing or follow-up questions are asked to more ideas from students. Results show that varied questioning techniques are practiced by teachers in class This aligns with the result of Fitriati et al. (2017) where it was found that questioning strategies used by teachers in class were varied. It was also observed that teachers mostly utilized repetition. Contrary to the results of this study, simplification was highly observed.

3.1 Level of Speaking ability

It is reflected in table 2 that the mean scores for the speaking ability garnered an overall mean of 3.63, described as high with a standard deviation of 0.35. The high level is attributed to all other indicators garnering high levels of description. This means that speaking ability in terms of Grammar, Vocabulary and Comprehension is very much manifested by the students.

Table 2

Level of Speaking Ability

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
Grammar	3.63	0.40	High
Vocabulary	3.57	0.42	High
Comprehension	3.69	0.39	High
Overall	3.63	0.35	High

The highest speaking ability based on the three indicators is comprehension. It garnered a mean score of 3.69 with a standard deviation of 0.39; Grammar got a mean score of 3.63 with a standard deviation of 0.40; Finally, the lowest mean score of 3.57 belonged to Vocabulary with a standard deviation of 0.42.

It should be noted that all indicators of Speaking ability are all high. The prominent speaking Ability of students is comprehension. This means that students can clearly understand with less difficulty in understand the subject matter quickly. The high level for comprehension indicated that the level of speaking ability of the student is positive. This result is consistent with the study of Bailey and Meurers(2008), who explained that comprehension questions are a common task in real-life learning situations. The lowest Speaking is vocabulary. Despite the high rating, it cannot be denied that there are still some students who have encounter some issues in

dealing with unfamiliar words. Though the occurrences might be relatively low, the issue persists for some students. The results can be attributed to the results of Zhang (2014) which stated that Vocabulary learning is cognitively challenging.

3.2 Significant of the relationship between the Questioning Techniques and Speaking Ability

A main purpose of this study was to determine whether the questioning techniques of the teacher have a significant relationship with the speaking Ability of students. Person r was used to determine the correlation between the two variables. The result is reflected in table 3.

Table 3

Correlation between Teachers' Questioning Techniques and Students Speaking Ability

Variables	Mean	SD	r Value	p Value
Teachers' Questioning Techniques	3.90	0.40	-0.078 ^{ns}	0.283
Students' Speaking Ability	3.63	0.35		

Legend: ns- Not Significant at $\alpha=0.05$

The result show that the questioning techniques of the teacher versus the speaking Ability of the student yielded an r-value of -0.078 and a p-value of 0.283. The p-value is greater than 0.05. This means that the result is not statistically significant and that the null hypotheses is retained. The null hypothesis being "there is no significant relationship between questioning techniques and the speaking Ability.

The result of the study is contrary to the results of Wahyudi (2017) and Eliyasun, et al. (2018), both studies found that Questioning Techniques improved the speaking ability of the students. It should be noted that there are differences in the indicators used in the study of Wahyudi. The study involved five indicators: Accent, Grammar, Vocabulary, Fluency and Comprehension. On the other hand, Eliyasun used only three indicators: Accuracy, Fluency and Comprehensibility. The difference in the results could be rooted in the distinction of the indicators. The current study only involved three indicators. The difference in the results is justified by Costa and Remedios (2014) who stated that using different methods has resulted different results.

4. Conclusion

The following conclusions were drawn based on the result. The teacher's questioning techniques are high for simplification, rephrasing, decomposition, repetition, and probing. In addition, the student's speaking ability is high for Comprehension, Grammar, and Vocabulary. Despite the results of both Questioning techniques and Speaking ability manifesting high scores it was found that there is no significant relationship between the questioning techniques of the teacher and the student's speaking ability. As such, questioning techniques of the teacher does not affect the speaking ability of students in terms of Grammar, Vocabulary, and Comprehension. In line with the result of the research, teachers may adopt another strategy when it comes to evaluating the speaking ability of the student. The study also poses implication for further research. This study can serve as a springboard for further studies down the line. It is imperative explore different studies not limited to questioning techniques and speaking ability but rather other areas which are involved with the learning of students.

5. References

- Bailey, S., & Meurers, D. (2008). *Diagnosing meaning errors in short answers to reading comprehension questions*. 107-115. <https://doi.org/10.3115/1631836.1631849>
- Connell, J. P., & Wellborn, J. G. (1991). Competence, autonomy, and relatedness: A motivational analysis of self-system processes. In M. Gunnar & L. A. Sroufe (Eds.), *Minnesota symposium on child psychology* (Vol. 23, pp. 43-77). Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

- Costa, L. D., & Remedios, R. (2014). Different methods, different results: Examining the implications of methodological divergence and implicit processes for achievement goal research. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 8(2), 162-179.
- De Guzman, M. M. A., & Macapagal, M. E. (2020). Pangarap ko, pangarap natin: The role of hope as a mediator between social support and school engagement among Filipino public school students. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 9(6), 25-36. <https://doi.org/10.5861/ijrse.2020.5030>
- Eliyasun, E., Rosnija, E., & Salam, U. (2018). Improving student's speaking ability through guided questions. *Jurnal Pendidikan dan Pembelajaran Khatulistiwa*, 7(1).
- Fitriati, S. W., Isfara, G. A. V., & Trisanti, N. (2017). Teachers' questioning strategies to elicit students' verbal responses in EFL classes at a secondary school. *English Review: Journal of English Education*, 5(2), 217-226.
- Fraenkel, Jack R., & Wallen, N. E. (2009). *How to design and evaluate research in education*. New York. McGraw-Hill Companies.
- Hsieh, T.-L. (2016). motivation categories in college students' learning engagement behaviors and outcomes in Taiwan: An application of cluster analysis. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 5(4), 19-30. <https://doi.org/10.5861/ijrse.2016.1222>
- Hu, Y. L., Ching, G. S., & Chao, P.-C. (2012). Taiwan student engagement model: Conceptual framework and overview of psychometric properties. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 1(1), 69-90. <https://doi.org/10.5861/ijrse.2012.v1i1.19>
- Hu, Y. L., Hung, C.-H., & Ching, G. S. (2015). Student-faculty interaction: mediating between student engagement factors and educational outcome gains. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 4(1), 43-53. <https://doi.org/10.5861/ijrse.2014.800>
- Jhangiani, R. S., Chiang, I. C. A., Cuttler, C., & Leighton, D. C. (2019). *Research methods in psychology*. Kwantlen Polytechnic University.
- Leong, L., & Ahmadi, S. (2017). An analysis of factors influencing learners' English speaking skill. *International Journal of Research in English Education*, 2(1), 34-41. <https://www.sid.ir/en/journal/ViewPaper.aspx?id=520992>
- Long, A. (1980). *Pedagogi: Kaedah am mengajar*. Fajar Bakti.
- Pascual, L. P. (2019, January). Exposure to English linguistic environment and oral proficiency of first year college students in Davao del Norte. In *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on E-Education, E-Business, E-Management and E-Learning* (pp. 225-229).
- Shanmugavelu, G., Ariffin, K., Vadivelu, M., Mahayudin, Z., & Sundaram, M. A. R. (2020). Questioning techniques and teachers' role in the classroom. *Shanlax International Journal of Education*, 8(4), 45-49.
- Tacadena, J.E. (2021). Classroom management and students' learning in Mathematics. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 5(3), 418-423. <https://doi.org/10.47772/IJRIS.2021.5328>
- Wahyudi, D. (2017). The use of questioning technique to enhance students' speaking ability. *Indonesian Journal of Integrated English Language Teaching*, 3(1).
- Walsh, J. A., & Sattes, B. (2015). *Questioning for classroom discussion*. Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- Zhang, X. (2014). A longitudinal study of receptive vocabulary breadth knowledge growth and vocabulary fluency development.

